

DOMINATION IN OPERATION ON BIPOLAR FUZZY GRAPHS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we obtain the bounds of the domination number in operations on bipolar fuzzy graphs like join, Cartesian product, composition, cross product and strong product.

Key Words: Bipolar fuzzy graphs, Domination & Domination Number

1. Introduction:

The first definition of fuzzy graphs was proposed by Kafmann, from the fuzzy relations introduced by Zadeh. Although Rosenfeld introduced another elaborated definition, including fuzzy vertex and fuzzy edges, and several fuzzy analogs of graph theoretic concepts such as paths, cycles, connectedness and etc. The concept of domination in fuzzy graphs was investigated by A. Somasundaram, S. Somasundaram and A. Somasundaram present the concepts of independent domination, total domination, connected domination of fuzzy graphs. Akram introduced the concept of bipolar fuzzy graphs, he discussed the concept of isomorphism of these graphs, and investigated some of their important properties, also defined some operations on bipolar fuzzy graphs. In this paper, we obtain the bonds of the domination number in operations on bipolar fuzzy graphs like join, Cartesian product, composition, cross product and strong product.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, some basic definitions related to bipolar fuzzy are given.

A bipolar fuzzy graph (BFG) is of the form $G = (V, E)$ where

i) $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ such that $\mu_1^+ : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu_1^- : X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$

ii) $E \subset V \times V$ where $\mu_2^+ : V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu_2^- : V \times V \rightarrow [-1, 0]$

Such that $\mu_{2_{ij}}^+ = \mu_2^+(v_i v_j) \leq \min(\mu_1^+(v_i), \mu_1^+(v_j))$ and

$$\mu_{2_{ij}}^- = \mu_2^-(v_i v_j) \leq \max(\mu_1^-(v_i), \mu_1^-(v_j)) \text{ for all } (v_i, v_j) \in E.$$

A bipolar fuzzy graph (BFG) $G = (V, E)$ is called strong if $\mu_2^+(v_i, v_j) = \max(\mu_1^+(v_i), \mu_1^+(v_j))$ and $\mu_2^-(v_i, v_j) = \min(\mu_1^-(v_i), \mu_1^-(v_j))$ for all $(v_i, v_j) \in E$.

A bipolar fuzzy graph (BFG) $G = (V, E)$ is called complete if $\mu_2^+(v_i, v_j) = \min(\mu_1^+(v_i), \mu_1^+(v_j))$ and $\mu_2^-(v_i, v_j) = \max(\mu_1^-(v_i), \mu_1^-(v_j))$ for all $(v_i, v_j) \in V$.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a bipolar fuzzy graph. Then the cardinality of G is defined to be

$$|G| = \sum_{v_i \in V} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_1^+(v_i) + \mu_1^-(v_i)}{2} \right) + \sum_{(v_i, v_j) \in E} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_2^+(v_i v_j) + \mu_2^-(v_i v_j)}{2} \right)$$

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a bipolar fuzzy graph. Then the vertex cardinality of G is defined by

$$|V| = \sum_{v_i \in V} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_1^+(v_i) + \mu_2^-(v_j)}{2} \right) \text{ for all } v_j \in V.$$

The number of vertices (the cardinality of V) is called the order of a BFG and is defined by

$$O(G) = \sum_{v_i \in V} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_1^+(v_i) + \mu_1^-(v_i)}{2} \right)$$

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a bipolar fuzzy graph. Then the edge cardinality of G is defined by

$$|E| = \sum_{(v_i, v_j) \in E} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_2^+(v_i v_j) + \mu_2^-(v_i v_j)}{2} \right).$$

The number of edges (the cardinality of E) is called the size of a BFG and is defined by

$$S(G) = \sum_{(v_i, v_j) \in E} \left(\frac{1 + \mu_2^+(v_i v_j) + \mu_2^-(v_i v_j)}{2} \right) \text{ for all } (v_i v_j) \in E.$$

The degree of a vertex v in a BFG, $G(V, E)$ is defined to be sum of the cardinality of strong arcs incident at v . It is denoted by $d_G(v)$. The minimum degree of G is $\delta(G) = \min\{d_G(v) / v \in V\}$ The maximum degree of G

$$\text{is } \Delta(G) = \max\{d_G(v)/v \in V\}.$$

The two vertices v_i and v_j are said to be effective neighbours in BFG if either one of the following conditions holds

- i) $\mu_2^+(v_i v_j) > 0$ and $\mu_2^-(v_i v_j) = 0$
- ii) $\mu_2^+(v_i v_j) = 0$ and $\mu_2^-(v_i v_j) < 0$
- iii) $\mu_2^+(v_i v_j) > 0$ and $\mu_2^-(v_i v_j) < 0, (v_i, v_j) \in E$

The complement of a BFG, $G = (V, E)$ is a BFG $\overline{G} = (\overline{V}, \overline{E})$, where

- i) $\overline{V} = V$
- ii) $\overline{\mu_{ii}^+} = \mu_{ii}^+$ and $\overline{\mu_{ii}^-} = \mu_{ii}^-$ for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.
- iii) $\overline{\mu_{2ij}^+} = \min(\mu_{i1}^+, \mu_{1j}^+) - \mu_{2ij}^+$ and
 $\overline{\mu_{2ij}^-} = \max(\mu_{ii}^-, \mu_{jj}^-) - \mu_{2ij}^-$ for all $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

An edge (u, v) is said to be strong edge in BFG, $G = (V, E)$ if $\mu_2^+(u, v) \geq (\mu_2^+)^{\infty}(u, v), \mu_2^-(u, v) \leq (\mu_2^-)^{\infty}(u, v)$

Where $\mu_2^+(u, v) = \max\{(\mu_2^+)^k(u, v) / k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and

$$\mu_2^-(u, v) = \min\{(\mu_2^-)^k(u, v) / k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$$

A vertex u be a vertex in BFG, $G = (V, E)$ then $N(u) = \{v, v \in V \text{ and } (u, v) \text{ is a strong arc in } G\}$ is called neighbourhood of u in G . A vertex $u \in V$ of a BFG, $G = (V, E)$ is said to be isolated vertex if $\mu_2^+(u, v) = 0$ and $\mu_2^-(u, v) = 0$ for all $v \in V, u \neq v$ That is $N(u) = \emptyset$. Thus an isolated vertex does not dominate any other vertex of G . Let $G = (V, E)$ be a BFG on V . Let $u, v \in V$, we say that u dominates v in G if there exists a strong edge between them.

Note:

- i) For any $u, v \in V$ of u dominates v then v dominates u and hence domination is a symmetric relation on V .
- ii) For any $v \in V, N(v)$ is precisely the set of all vertices in V which are dominated by v .
- iii) If $\mu_2^+(u, v) < (\mu_2^+)^{\infty}(u, v)$ and $\mu_2^-(u, v) > (\mu_2^-)^{\infty}(u, v)$ for all $u, v \in V$. Then the dominating set of G is V .

A subset S of V is called dominating set in G if for every $v \in V - S$, there exist $u \in S$ such that u dominates v . A dominating set S of a BFG is said to be minimal dominating set if no proper subset of S is a dominating set. The Minimum cardinality among all minimal dominating set is called the lower domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_{\text{bif}}(G)$. The Maximum cardinality among all minimal dominating set is called the upper domination number of G and is denoted by $\Gamma_{\text{bif}}(G)$.

3. Main Results:

Definition 3.1:

Let $A_1 = (\mu_{A_1}^+, \mu_{A_1}^-)$ and $A_2 = (\mu_{A_2}^+, \mu_{A_2}^-)$ be bipolar fuzzy subsets of V_1 and V_2 in which $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$ and let $B_1 = (\mu_{B_1}^+, \mu_{B_1}^-)$ and $B_2 = (\mu_{B_2}^+, \mu_{B_2}^-)$ be bipolar fuzzy subsets of $V_1 \times V_2$ and $V_2 \times V_1$ respectively. Then we denote the join of two bipolar fuzzy graphs G_1 and G_2 by $G_1 + G_2 = (A_1 + A_2, B_1 + B_2)$ and defined as follows

$$\begin{cases} (\mu_{A_1}^+ + \mu_{A_2}^+)(x) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^+(x), \mu_{A_2}^+(x)) \\ (\mu_{A_1}^- + \mu_{A_2}^-)(x) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^-(x), \mu_{A_2}^-(x)) \text{ if } x \in V_1 \cup V_2 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} (\mu_{B_1}^+ + \mu_{B_2}^+)(xy) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^+(xy), \mu_{B_2}^+(xy)) & \begin{cases} (\mu_{B_1}^+ + \mu_{B_2}^+)(xy) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x), \mu_{B_1}^+(y)) \\ (\mu_{B_1}^- + \mu_{B_2}^-)(xy) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x), \mu_{B_2}^-(y)) \text{ if } xy \in E_1' \end{cases} \\ (\mu_{B_1}^- + \mu_{B_2}^-)(xy) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^-(xy), \mu_{B_2}^-(xy)) \text{ if } xy \in E_1 \cap E_2 \end{cases}$$

Where E_1' is the set of all edges joining the nodes of V_1 and V_2 .

Theorem 3.1:

Let G_1 and G_2 be a bipolar fuzzy graphs and D_1 and D_2 be the minimum dominating set of G_1 and G_2 respectively. Then $\gamma(G_1 + G_2) = \min(|D_1|, |D_2|) = \min(\gamma(G_1), \gamma(G_2))$

Proof:

First we prove D_1 and D_2 be the dominating set of $G_1 + G_2$. If $y \in G_1$, obviously is dominating by $x \in D_1$, since D_1 is the dominating set of G_1 .

Definition 3.2:

The Cartesian product $G_1 \times G_2$ is the pair (A,B) of bipolar fuzzy sets defined on the Cartesian product

$G_1^* \times G_2^*$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \mu_A^+(x_1, x_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(x_2)) \\ \mu_A^-(x_1, x_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(x_2)) \text{ for all } (x_1, x_2) \in V_1 \times V_2 \end{cases} \begin{cases} \mu_B^+(x_1, x_2)(x, y_2) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{B_2}^+(x_2, y_2)) \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, x_2)(x, y_2) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{B_2}^-(x_2, y_2)) \text{ for all } x_2, y_2 \in E_2 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \mu_B^+(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1, y_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(z)) \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1, y_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(z)) \text{ or all } x_1, y_1 \in E_1 \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.2:

Let D_1 and D_2 be a minimum dominating set of bipolar fuzzy graph G_1 & G_2 respectively. Then

$$\gamma(G_1 \times G_2) = \min\{|D_1 \times V_2|, |V_1 \times D_2|\}.$$

Proof:

Now we prove $D_1 \times V_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$. Let $(u_1, u_2) \notin D_1 \times V_2$. Hence $u_1 \notin D_1$.

Let D_1 is a dominating set of G_1 , there exist $v_1 \in D_1$ such that

$$\mu_{B_1}^+(u_1, v_1) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1), \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1))$$

$$\mu_{B_1}^-(u_1, v_1) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1), \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1))$$

If $(v_1, u_2) \in D_1 \times V_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u_1, u_2)(v_1, u_2)) &= \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(u_1, v_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) \quad \forall u_2 \in V_2 & \mu_B^-((u_1, u_2)(v_1, u_2)) &= \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(u_1, v_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1)), \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) & &= \max((\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1)), \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \\ &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) & &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \\ &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(v_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) & &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(v_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1, u_2) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_1, u_2) & &= \mu_B^-(u_1, u_2) \vee \mu_B^-(v_1, u_2) \end{aligned}$$

This implies every $(u_1, u_2) \notin D_1 \times V_2$ there exist a vertex $(v_1, u_2) \in D_1 \times V_2$ such that there is a strong arc between (u_1, u_2) and (v_1, u_2) . Therefore $D_1 \times V_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$. Similarly we prove $V_1 \times D_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$.

Next we prove $D_1 \times V_2$ and $V_1 \times D_2$ is a minimum dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$. Suppose $D_1 \times V_2$ is not a minimal. There exist a vertex $(x_1, u_2) \in D_1 \times V_2$ such that $\{(D_1 \times V_2) - (x_1, u_2)\}$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$. Let $(u_1, u_2) \in D_1 \times V_2$, (u_1, u_2) dominates (x_1, u_2) . Since $D_1 \times V_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$. Therefore we get u_1 dominates $x_1 \in D_1$. Clearly $D_1 - x_1$ is a dominating set of G_1 . This is contradict to our assumption D_1 is minimal. Therefore $D_1 \times V_2$ is a minimal dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$.

Similarly we find $V_1 \times D_2$ is a minimum dominating set of $G_1 \times G_2$.

Therefore $\gamma(G_1 \times G_2) = \min\{|D_1 \times V_2|, |V_1 \times D_2|\}$.

Definition 3.3:

The composition $G_1[G_2]$ is the pair (A, B) of bipolar fuzzy sets defined on the composition

$G_1^* [G_2^*]$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \mu_A^+(x_1, x_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(x_2)) \\ \mu_A^-(x_1, x_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(x_2)) \text{ for all } (x_1, x_2) \in V_1 \times V_2 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \mu_B^+(x_1, x_2)(x, y_2) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{B_2}^+(x_2, y_2)) \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, x_2)(x, y_2) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{B_2}^-(x_2, y_2)) \text{ for all } x_2, y_2 \in E_2 \end{cases} \begin{cases} \mu_B^+(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1, y_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(z)) \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1, y_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(z)) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \mu_B^+((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) = \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(x_2), \mu_{A_2}^+(y_2), \mu_{B_1}^+(x_1, y_1)) \\ \mu_B^-((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) = \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(x_2), \mu_{A_2}^-(y_2), \mu_{B_1}^-(x_1, y_1)) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.3:

Let D_1, D_2 are minimum dominating sets of a bipolar fuzzy graphs G_1 and G_2 respectively. Then

$$\gamma(G_1 \circ G_2) = |D_1 \times D_2|.$$

Proof:

Let $(u, v) \notin D_1 \times D_2$.

Case (i): $u \notin D_1$ and $v \in D_2$

Let $u \notin D_1$, there exist $u_1 \in D_1$ such that u_1 dominates u . Then

$$\mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1)) \quad \mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1))$$

Now $(u_1, v) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u,v)(u_1,v)) &= \mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1)) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u_1, v) \\ \mu_B^-((u,v)(u_1,v)) &= \mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \\ &= \max((\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1)) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u_1, v) \end{aligned}$$

Hence (u_1, v) dominates (u, v) .

Case (ii): $u \in D_1$ and $v \notin D_2$

Let $v_2 \in D_2$, such that

$$\mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2) = \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2))$$

$$\mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2) = \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))$$

Now $(u, v_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u,v)(u,v_2)) &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2)) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_2}^+(v)) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v_2) \\ \mu_B^-((u,v)(u,v_2)) &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence (u, v_2) dominates (u, v) .

Case (iii): $u \notin D_1$ and $v \notin D_2$

D_1 and D_2 be the minimum dominating sets of G_1 and G_2 .

Therefore, there exist $u_1 \in D_1$ and $v_2 \in D_2$ such that

$$\mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1))$$

$$\mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1))$$

$$\text{and } \mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2) = \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2)) \quad \mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2) = \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))$$

Let $(u_1, v_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u,v)(u_1,v_2)) &= \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2), \mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1)) \\ &= \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2), \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^+(u_1, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^-((u,v)(u_1,v_2)) &= \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2), \mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1)) \\ &= \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2), (\mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1))) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \circ \mu_{A_2})^-(u_1, v_2) \\ &= \max(\mu_A^-(u, v), \mu_A^-(u_1, v_2)) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we get (u_1, v_2) dominates

(u, v) in $G_1 \circ G_2$. This implies that $D_1 \times D_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \circ G_2$.

Now we prove $D_1 \times D_2$ is minimum. Let $(x_1, x_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$, $x_1 \in D_1$ and $x_2 \in D_2$. By our assumption D_1 and D_2 are minimal dominating set of G_1 and G_2 respectively. Therefore $D_1 - x_1$ and $D_2 - x_2$ are not a dominating set. Clearly we get $(D_1 \times D_2) - (x_1 \times x_2)$ is not a minimal dominating set. This implies that $D_1 \times D_2$ is minimal dominating set of $G_1 \circ G_2$.

Therefore we get $\gamma(G_1 \circ G_2) = |D_1 \times D_2|$.

Figure 3.2

In figure 3.2 the minimum dominating set of G_1 and G_2 are $D_1 = \{a, c\}$ and $D_2 = \{f\}$ respectively. The minimum dominating set of $G_1 \circ G_2$ is $\{af, cf\}$.

Definition 3.4:

The cross product of $G_1 * G_2$ is the pair (A, B) of bipolar fuzzy sets defined on the cross product $G_1 * G_2$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \mu_A^+(x_1, x_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(x_2)) \\ \mu_A^-(x_1, x_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(x_2)) \\ \mu_B^+(x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1), \mu_{B_2}^+(x_2 y_2)) \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1), \mu_{B_2}^-(x_2 y_2)) \end{cases}$$

for all $x_1 y_1 \in E_1$ & $x_2 y_2 \in E_2$

Theorem 3.4:

Let D_1 and D_2 be the minimum dominating set of bipolar fuzzy graph G_1 and G_2 respectively. Then

$$\gamma_{bf}(G_1 * G_2) = \min\{|D_1 \times V_2|, |V_1 \times D_2|\}$$

Proof:

Let $(u_1, u_2) \notin D_1 \times V_2$. Hence $u_1 \notin D_1$.

Since D_1 is a dominating set of G_1 , there exist a vertex $v_1 \in D_1$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{B_1}^+(u_1, v_1) &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1), \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1)) \\ \mu_{B_1}^-(u_1, v_1) &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1), \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1)) \end{aligned}$$

Let $(v_1 v_2) \in D_1 \times V_2$ such that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A^+(u_1 u_2) &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2)) \\ \mu_A^-(u_1 u_2) &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2)) \end{aligned}$$

and
$$\mu_A^+(v_1 v_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(v_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2))$$

$$\mu_A^-(v_1 v_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(v_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u_1 u_2)(v_1 v_2)) &= \mu_A^+(u_1 u_2) \wedge \mu_A^+(v_1 v_2) & \mu_B^-((u_1 u_2)(v_1 v_2)) &= \mu_A^-(u_1 u_2) \vee \mu_A^-(v_1 v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2)) & &= (\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2)) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(v_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(u_2) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2)) & &= (\mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(v_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(u_2) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2)) \\ &= \mu_{B_1}^+(u_1 v_1) \wedge \mu_{B_2}^+(u_2 v_2) & &= \mu_{B_1}^-(u_1 v_1) \vee \mu_{B_2}^-(u_2 v_2) \end{aligned}$$

This implies there is strong arc between (u_1, u_2) and (v_1, v_2) .

Therefore (u_1, u_2) is dominating by (v_1, v_2) .

This implies $D_1 \times V_2$ is a dominating by $(G_1 * G_2)$.

Similarly we prove $V_1 \times D_2$ is a dominating by $(G_1 * G_2)$.

Hence $\gamma_{bf}(G_1 * G_2) = \min\{|D_1 \times V_2|, |V_1 \times D_2|\}$.

Definition 3.6:

The strong product $G_1 \otimes G_2$ of G_1 is the pair (A, B) of bipolar fuzzy sets defined on the strong product $G_1 \otimes G_2$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \mu_A^+(x_1, x_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(x_2)) & \mu_B^+(x, x_2)(x, y_2) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(x), \mu_{B_2}^+(x_2 y_2)) \\ \mu_A^-(x_1, x_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(x_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(x_2)) \text{ for all } (x_1, x_2) \in V_1 \times V_2 & \mu_B^-(x, x_2)(x, y_2) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(x), \mu_{B_2}^-(x_2 y_2)) \text{ for all } x \in V_1 \& x_2 y_2 \in E_2 \\ \mu_B^+(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1), \mu_{A_2}^+(z)) & \\ \mu_B^-(x_1, z)(y_1, z) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1), \mu_{A_2}^-(z)) \text{ for all } z \in V_2 \& \text{ for all } x_1 y_1 \in E_1 & \\ \mu_B^+((x_1 x_2)(y_1 y_2)) = \min(\mu_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1), \mu_{B_2}^+(x_2 y_2)) & \\ \mu_B^-((x_1 x_2)(y_1 y_2)) = \max(\mu_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1), \mu_{B_2}^-(x_2 y_2)) \text{ for all } (x_1 y_1) \in E_1 \& (x_2 y_2) \in E_2 & \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.5:

Let D_1, D_2 are minimum dominating sets of a bipolar fuzzy graph G_1 and G_2 respectively. Then $\gamma(G_1 \otimes G_2) = |D_1 \times D_2|$.

Proof:

Let $(u, v) \notin D_1 \times D_2$.

Case (i): $u \notin D_1$ and $v \in D_2$

Let $u \notin D_1$, there exist $u_1 \in D_1$ such that u_1 dominates u . Then

$$\mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1))$$

$$\mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1))$$

Now $(u_1, v) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u,v)(u_1,v)) &= \mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1)) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u_1, v) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^-((u,v)(u_1,v)) &= \mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \\ &= \max((\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1)) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v)) \quad \text{Hence } (u_1, v) \text{ dominates } (u, v). \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u_1, v) \end{aligned}$$

Case (ii): $u \in D_1$ and $v \notin D_2$

Let $v_2 \in D_2$, such that

$$\mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2) = \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2))$$

$$\mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2) = \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))$$

Now $(u, v_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u,v)(u, v_2)) &= \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2)) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_2}^+(v)) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^-((u,v)(u, v_2)) &= \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2)) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence (u, v_1) dominates (u, v) .

Case (iii): $u \notin D_1$ and $v \notin D_2$

D_1 and D_2 be the minimum dominating sets of G_1 and G_2 .

Therefore, there exist $u_1 \in D_1$ and $v_2 \in D_2$ such that

$$\mu_{B_1}^+(u, u_1) = \min(\mu_{A_1}^+(u), \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1))$$

$$\mu_{B_1}^-(u, u_1) = \max(\mu_{A_1}^-(u), \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1))$$

and
$$\mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2) = \min(\mu_{A_2}^+(v), \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2))$$

$$\mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2) = \max(\mu_{A_2}^-(v), \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))$$

Let $(u_1, v_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^+((u, v)(u_1, v_2)) &= \min(\mu_{B_2}^+(u, u_1), \mu_{B_2}^+(v, v_2)) \\ &= \min((\mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1)), (\mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2))) \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^+(u) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v) \wedge \mu_{A_1}^+(u_1) \wedge \mu_{A_2}^+(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u, v) \wedge (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^+(u_1, v_2) \\ &= \min(\mu_A^+(u, v), \mu_A^+(u_1, v_2)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B^-((u, v)(u_1, v_2)) &= \max(\mu_{B_2}^-(u, u_1), \mu_{B_2}^-(v, v_2)) \\ &= \max((\mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1)), (\mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2))) \quad \text{Therefore we get } (u_1, v_2) \text{ dominates } (u, v) \text{ in } G_1 \otimes G_2. \\ &= \mu_{A_1}^-(u) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v) \vee \mu_{A_1}^-(u_1) \vee \mu_{A_2}^-(v_2) \\ &= (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u, v) \vee (\mu_{A_1} \otimes \mu_{A_2})^-(u_1, v_2) \\ &= \max(\mu_A^-(u, v), \mu_A^-(u_1, v_2)) \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $D_1 \times D_2$ is a dominating set of $G_1 \otimes G_2$.

Now we prove $D_1 \times D_2$ is minimum.

Let $(x_1, x_2) \in D_1 \times D_2$, $x_1 \in D_1$ and $x_2 \in D_2$.

By our assumption D_1 and D_2 are minimal dominating set of G_1 and G_2 respectively. Therefore $D_1 - x_1$ and $D_2 - x_2$ are not a dominating set. Clearly we get $(D_1 \times D_2) - (x_1 \times x_2)$ is not a minimal dominating set. This implies that $D_1 \times D_2$ is minimal dominating set of $G_1 \otimes G_2$

Therefore $\gamma(G_1 \otimes G_2) = |D_1 \times D_2|$.

Figure 3.3

In figure 3.3 the minimum dominating set of G_1 and G_2 are $D_1=\{a,c\}$ and $D_2=\{e\}$ respectively. The minimum dominating set of $G_1 \circ G_2$ is $\{ae,ce\}$.

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